

IMPROVEMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN MANAGEMENT: BASIC CONTENT, ASSSMENT DIRECTIONS

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Thanks to the reforms that are being carried out for the stable and effective development of the economy, it is possible to implement deep structural changes in the economy in a short period of time, develop production and service provision, ensure the growth of the population's income, stable development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, and the activities of the banking and financial system. Significant progress was made in the development of scientific projects.

Operating enterprises play an important role in achieving these achievements. The role of operating enterprises is of great importance. Currently, there are 475,197 enterprises and organizations of various types of economic activity in our republic, of which 13,239,600 people are working and contributing to these achievements.

Based on this, one of the main factors in the development of the economies of enterprises is the human factor. Today, the management of labor potential in enterprises and its effective use require modern management. The number, capacity, formation, development, and composition of employees are of great importance in enterprise management. The effectiveness of human resources, in particular, has a direct impact on the enterprise's results.

Assessing the leader's performance is a pressing issue. An effective manager should pay equal attention to two areas of his activity: interaction with the external environment and improving the organization's internal environment. In this sense, employee performance evaluation helps to develop relationships within the company. Therefore, the increasing attention to personnel evaluation and

certification is not accidental. Managers thus strive to strengthen the internal ranks and increase the stability of the organization in adverse economic conditions.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ShavkatMirziyoyev, to the OliyMajlis, he stated that "... business entities and new jobs created in each industry, sector, region, and district will be the main criterion for evaluating the activities of the leaders of these structures..." [Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoyev to the OliyMajlis, "People's Word," January 25, 2020, #19 (7521).].

The reform of the management system in economic sectors in our country requires fundamentally new qualities—first of all, new knowledge, skills, and qualifications from the management staff. The special role and importance of the management employee depend on the competition between producers of goods and services.

There are problems related to the reform of our country's economy in the context of the transition to market relations. In particular, there are existing problems in enterprises and firms, including the low competitiveness of their products, the significant inefficiency of business organization, and lagging behind developed countries in the field of management in all its forms. Our country's enterprises and organizations frequently employ outdated management methods. There is a great interest in evaluating the mental work of managers. Also, the role of performance evaluation in improving the efficiency of enterprises and organizations is constantly increasing. We can see this for the following reasons: the difficulty of measuring managerial activity as a type of intellectual labor compared to the physical labor of workers, operators, and other categories of technical personnel. In this case, there are almost no production standards directly related to the manager's management work, and the relationship between the performance of the individual manager and the overall final results becomes increasingly difficult in the context of a deepened division of labor. Modern methods are needed to judge the work of managers. This is because management work is getting more complicated and important because there are so many functions and professional differences. This means that judging

the work of all types of managers is becoming more important. According to the above, one of the most pressing issues today is the evaluation and comprehensive analysis of the management staff's work efficiency.

Analysis of the literature on the topic. A manager's constant control over the activities of his subordinates will have a positive effect. Assessment is a set of several instrumental systems tightly connected with the main functions of facility management. Evaluation assumes the existence of evaluation criteria and an evaluation scale.

References:

1. Modern principles of management acquire a unique expression and an independent essence in the management of employees, labor teams, relations processes in production [M.M. Yuldasheva.
2. "Improving personnel management in corporate structures in the context of modernization of the national economy". 08.00.13 - "Management and Marketing", i.f.n. academic degree dissertation. TDIU, -T:, 2010. -151 p.].
3. Management principles provide for clear regulation of the rights and obligations of employees, as well as managers of various levels of the enterprise management system. In the process of work, it is necessary to know the responsibilities of the leader and the employees. This is important in achieving the company's goals.